

GREAT LAKES: A LOOK TO THE FUTURE

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Trace toxic contaminants will be the major research focus in the years ahead, since our inland seas appear to be especially sensitive to contaminants. During the 1970s, however, attention centered on pollution from municipal sewage treatment plants. By year 2000 controls are predicted to reduce phosphorus inputs to the Great Lakes from municipal sources by more than half current levels. Although this reduction will likely result in an overall improvement in water quality, it may also result in small reductions in fish yields. During the 1980s and 1990s it will be important to evaluate the effects of phosphorus control and other programs to determine whether pollution control programs have been cost-effective. Finally, because of water shortages around the world, water quantity will emerge as a major Great Lakes issue.

1. Introduction

The Great Lakes, which make up North America's inland sea, contain more fresh water and cover more area than the total of all rivers, lakes, and impoundments in the United States and have a coastline that is longer than the Atlantic and Gulf Coasts combined. They cover an area greater than the states of New York, New Jersey, Connecticut, Vermont, New Hampshire, Rhode Island, and Massachusetts put together. Currently, more than one-third of Canada's population and one-eighth of the United States' population are concentrated along the Lakes' shores.

Considerable research has been performed on this massive and valuable resource. Importantly, this research has had a major payoff. In many areas of the Lakes trends toward degradation have been stopped or improvements in environmental quality have actually occurred. For example, as a result of a comprehensive management effort based on information gained through careful research, Lake Erie has dramatically improved. No longer do people talk of Lake Erie as a "dead" lake. Instead, recreation on and along Lake Erie is booming, and the lake is now considered by many to support one of the finest sport fisheries in the world.

Despite considerable cause for optimism, the future of the Great Lakes is uncertain. Pollution

by toxic substances and the eutrophication of the Great Lakes will continue to be important areas for study. As quality fresh water becomes an increasingly scarce commodity, determining how to use wisely the vast quantity of water held by the Lakes will also be a major research issue. Finally, during the 1970s it became clear that the Lakes cannot be managed using the traditional separate problem approach; instead, they must be managed as a total ecosystem. How to do this is a major question to be resolved in the years ahead.

2. Toxic Substances

Currently, contamination by trace toxic contaminants, or xenobiotics, is the major environmental problem facing the Great Lakes. More than 30,000 chemical compounds of industrial or commercial significance are used in the United States [1]. More specific to the Great Lakes basin, a recent study by Sullivan and Delfino [2] documented over 700 chemicals used in the lower Fox River Basin, which drains into Lake Michigan's Green Bay. The use of chemicals is bound to grow as our society becomes further dependent on technology. At present, about 1,000 new compounds are developed each year [1]. If only a small percentage of these newly produced chemicals enter the Great Lakes, the potential for ecological problems will be great. Thus, understanding the effects of xenobiotics that gain access to the Lakes will be a critical research need for years to come.

The Great Lakes have been particularly susceptible to toxic contaminant problems, probably more so than any other place in the world. As a result, considerable research has already been conducted and management actions taken. The results have been positive. For example, the preponderance of evidence indicates that PCB levels in Great Lakes fish, which for some species are several million times greater than that in the water, are going down. The prognosis for the future is therefore optimistic; environmental levels of contaminants whose input into the lakes has been reduced or eliminated should decrease. However, it would be naive to think that the problem is solved. Many of the contaminants that enter the Lakes eventually find their way to the deepest trenches. The long-term significance of accumulations of sediments in these areas is not known. Perhaps burial in the deep trenches is a safe disposal mechanism for anthropogenic

contaminants. Alternately, contaminated deep sediments could be a time bomb that will haunt future generations.

While the need to study xenobiotic contamination is well established, the level of risk to humans from exposure to Great Lakes toxic contaminants is not. Putting the proper perspective on risks, and balancing the risks with the costs of reducing them, will be a major challenge facing both scientists and resource managers.

One way to put risks in perspective is to view them in relation to one another. For example, there has been much concern regarding the risks of cancer from eating Great Lakes fish contaminated with high levels of polychlorinated biphenyls (PCBs). However, compared to other risks commonly faced by most individuals (driving a car, flying in an airplane, using electric power), the risk of dying from eating contaminated fish (based on available information) is quite low.

One specific area of toxic contaminant pollution that may be significant for the Great Lakes in the future is energy-related contaminants. The use of coal as an energy source is especially likely to increase in the Great Lakes area in the future. One group of contaminants associated with the burning of coal are the polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs). These compounds, some of which are known to be carcinogenic, enter the lakes largely through an atmospheric pathway. However, they are also found in coal ash. This ash is often wet-slurried. Lagoons holding this material and located adjacent to the Great Lakes (or tributaries to the Lakes) may contribute PAHs as a result of overflows, seepage, or other types of accidental discharge.

PAHs have been found in relatively high concentrations in *Pontoporeia hoyi*, the most abundant benthic organism in Lake Michigan. Eadie et al. [3] have estimated that PAH concentrations in these organisms are 10^4 to 10^5 times higher than in the overlying water. Bottom feeding fish in certain areas sometimes exhibit tumorous lesions that may be related to elevated PAH levels in the benthic invertebrates upon which they feed. In any case, if coal use continues to increase, the risk of PAH contamination is likely to draw as much attention as PCB contamination drew during the 1970s.

3. Eutrophication

The natural or artificial addition of nutrients to the Great Lakes, i.e., eutrophication, was a major research and management focus during the last decade. The Great Lakes eutrophication control program is, in fact, one of the best examples of international management of a shared resource. Millions of dollars have been spent, primarily for removing the nutrient phosphorus from sewage treatment plants.

By the year 2000 phosphorus inputs to the Great Lakes from U.S. municipal sources, despite population increases that increase sewage volume,

will be less than half the inputs during the early 1970s. This reduction will result from implementation of a 1 mg l^{-1} total phosphorus standard at treatment plants. Table 1, based on data from Heidtke et al. [4], gives reductions predicted for each lake. It shows that Lake Erie will experience the largest overall phosphorus reduction.

Table 1. Projections of Total Phosphorus Loads to the Great Lakes from U.S. Municipal Treatment Plants

	(Metric Tons/Yr)	
	Mid-1970s	2000
Lake Superior	180	90
Lake Huron	480	270
Lake Michigan	1,800	1,250
Lake Erie	7,900	3,450
Lake Ontario	2,570	850

What can be expected to result from the above phosphorus reduction? The answer is not clear, partly because of the unprecedented size of this pollution control experiment. In general, phytoplankton growth in the Lakes should be reduced. Reductions in phytoplankton should, in turn, result in some increase in macrophytes, improved transparency, and higher average annual oxygen concentrations, especially in embayments, harbors, and certain parts of Lake Erie. Populations of species associated with good water quality should also increase. Already, signs of improvement are appearing. Initial surveys of Lake Erie show considerable improvement of this lake. The potential of Lake Erie as a major sport fishery is now greater than ever.

Although the reduced phosphorus loads to the Great Lakes will generally benefit the sport fishery, the total fish yield of the Great Lakes may be reduced [5]. Fish yield reductions are likely to be greatest in lower Green Bay, main Lake Michigan, Saginaw Bay, Lake Ontario, and the western and central basins of Lake Erie.

The real evaluation of the eutrophication program will come in the years ahead. A major task will be to analyze the response of the Great Lakes ecosystem to the nutrient abatement program conducted during the 70s. This analysis will provide insight into what incremental management actions and what future eutrophication research should be conducted.

Another future concern related to eutrophication is pollution from land runoff. The state-of-the-art of nonpoint-source pollution is probably more advanced in the Great Lakes basin than anywhere [6]. Based on mid- to late-1970 data, about 50% of the total phosphorus load to the Great Lakes (excluding atmospheric inputs and shoreline erosion phosphorus) is attributable to rural and urban land runoff. By the year 2000, about 70% of the total phosphorus load will likely be due to

land runoff. However, not all of the nonpoint source total phosphorus load is bioavailable. In fact, less than half of the sediment phosphorus appears readily bioavailable [7]. Moreover, it is uncertain what effect measures to control land runoff pollution, such as conservation tillage, will have on the bioavailable fraction of pollutants in land runoff. Accordingly, while progress has been made in understanding the sources and amounts of nonpoint source pollution, much remains to be learned, particularly about the environmental chemistry and fate of nonpoint source pollutants.

4. Water Quantity

During the last decade water quality was the focus of Great Lakes attention. In the 1950s, however, water quantity was the premier issue. In the future, a resurgence of water quantity as a major issue can be expected.

The demand for quality fresh water is great throughout the world. Severe droughts continue to occur. In the United States, recent droughts in California and the northeast necessitated restrictive water conservation practices. Undoubtedly, the waters of Lake Ontario were eyed when the reservoirs serving New York City reached precariously low levels.

The need for fresh water has spurred considerable interest in exporting water out of the Great Lakes. Both the Sun Belt States and the Western States (where water is needed for energy development) have made overtures for Great Lakes water. Certainly the Great Lakes offer an abundant amount of fresh water. A diversion of $60 \text{ m}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$, less than the current diversion out of Lake Michigan through the Chicago Sanitary Canal, would supply the water needs of a city as large as New York. Nevertheless, a drop in lake levels of only a few centimeters has an important effect on the power produced at various locations along the system. Further, international treaties currently restrict the amount of Great Lakes water that can be diverted. Thus, despite the abundance of water in the Great Lakes, its use is not a straightforward issue. Furthermore, the value of the resource provides a rationale for additional water quality research. The potential value of the water will be realized only if its quality is maintained or improved.

5. Ecosystem Management

It is clear that cost-effective management of the Great Lakes will require that the Lakes be managed as an integrated system. Management actions applied to one lake or one use affect the other lakes or other uses. For example, a fisheries management plan cannot be developed for Lake Michigan without taking into account the influences this plan will have on Lake Erie. Nor can a toxics contaminant control program be implemented without understanding the economic implications of such a program. Just as modern medicine is beginning to develop an approach called "holistic" health care, whereby nutrition, stress management,

biofeedback, and other approaches are used to promote good health in humans (as opposed to the conventional patch-up method, which treats symptoms), an ecosystem or holistic management concept must be instituted to promote the good health of the Lakes.

Regarding pollution, applying an ecosystem management concept will require that the relative importance of all pollution sources be understood before cost-effective controls are established. For instance, atmospheric pollution is now known to be an important contributor of trace toxic contaminants and other pollutants to the Lakes. Controlling conventional pollutant discharges while ignoring atmospheric pollutants (the generation of which may occur far outside the Great Lakes Basin) may result in wasted public and private funds.

Application of an ecosystem management approach will not be straightforward and will be a major challenge of the future. The interrelationships between the physical, chemical, biological, social, and economic aspects are only beginning to be understood. But only through a systematic approach can the Lakes be managed effectively.

6. Summary

The Great Lakes are a national resource of massive size and importance. However, their full value to the many users of the system, both now and in the future, will only be realized if the quality of this water is maintained. One of the most serious threats facing this resource is the accumulation of trace toxic contaminants. Our knowledge of the environmental fate of these substances and their long-term effects must be increased. Regarding nutrient pollution (eutrophication) of the Great Lakes, much progress has been made. However, this progress may be negated unless a major effort is undertaken in the years ahead to evaluate the effectiveness of control programs and to determine what incremental actions, if any, must be taken in the future.

Over the last few years scientists have come to appreciate how important it is to view the Great Lakes as an ecosystem. We have not yet learned how to manage the Lakes as such, but we need to continually strive for that. The Great Lakes are an international heritage and a resource that, if properly used according to the knowledge gained through research and careful study, will be of unsurpassed economic and social value now and in the future.

7. References

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